

MAMMOGRAPHY AS EARLY SCREENING TOOL FOR BREAST CANCER AMONG HIGH RISK WOMEN AT ROYAL MEDICAL SERVICES IN JORDAN

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Abstract

Keywords: Breast cancer, women, mammogram etc.

Breast cancer (BC) is one of the leading causes of death among Jordanian cancer women; BC screening guidelines have a vital role in health promotion, cancer prevention, and/or early cancer diagnosis. BC screening tests among women with primary family-related i.e. mother and/or sisters in the same age of diagnosis must include an annual mammogram which is required earlier than others.

Objective: To assess mammogram s' findings among high-risk women to develop breast cancer in Jordan.

Methods: A retrospective study for 200 patients with a primary family history of breast cancer aged above 30 years old underwent a mammogram for breast cancer screening, conducted in the radiology department/Al Hussain Hospital and Military Cancer Center at Royal Medical Services (RMS) in Jordan between 2019 -2021.

Results: All participants were female, Married (78.0%, n= 234), and less than half (31.50%, n=61) were the age of (40-49). Furthermore, the analysis revealed that the majority of the 2 mammography results were suspicion mass (85.5%, n=171). More than half of them (55%, n=110) are on stage 4 of breast cancer. However, the right site (45.5%, n=90) was the most frequent site among all mammography scanning. Suspicion mass among females was associated with age (p=.000). Specifically; female patients at 40-49 and 50-59 years old.

Conclusion: Mammography detection of suspension mass of breast cancer is high. Most suspicious masses are discovered at stage four. Therefore, management is essential to develop strategies that will enhance the early identification of cancer by mammography, mainly for high-risk women.

Introduction

Early discovering of breast cancer and receiving proper cancer treatment are considered the most important methods to decrease the prevalence of death from breast cancer. However, when breast cancer is found early, small, and has not spread, the treatment becomes more effective. According to the Centers of Disease Control and prevention (CDC), the mammogram is considered the most effective method for early identification of breast cancer, when it is the treatment is easier (DCD, 2021). Having regular mammograms might decrease the mortality from breast cancer (Monticciolo et al., 2017). Currently, a mammogram is the best method to find breast cancer for most women of screening age (Saadatmand et al., 2019). Breast cancer is the most common malignancy among females. In 2020, there were about 2.3 million new breast cancer incidences and 684,996 deaths international (Sung et al., 2021). In Jordan, Breast cancer is the second most common cancer death after lung cancer (Abdel-Razeq, Mansour, and Jaddan, 2020).

Regular breast cancer screening is essential since it is sometimes found after symptoms appear. According to the American Cancer Society (ACS), screening tests are used to find cancer before symptoms appear. Nevertheless, screening describes the tests and exams that are used to determine the presence of disease in individuals who don't have symptoms. On the other hand, early detection is used to find and diagnose diseases earlier than waiting for symptoms to appear (ACS, 2021). Now, there are numerous reliable, practical, and cost-effective methods used for the early detection and screening of breast cancer (Coleman, 2017). However, the most valid and sensitive method for breast cancer screening and early detection is a mammogram (Barba et al., 2020). A mammogram is low-dose x-rays that can assist in finding breast cancer by detecting 4 changes in breast tissue. However, a screening mammogram is used to identify signs of breast cancer in the female who don't have any symptoms or problems (ACS, 2021). CDC recommendations are to start screening with a mammogram every year for all women the age of 40 years and more (CDC, 2021).

Material and methods

A retrospective study was performed to find the high risk women who underwent breast cancer screening with mammography at the radiology department/Al Hussain Hospital and Military Cancer Center at Royal Medical Services (RMS) in Jordan from 2019 to 2021. A total of 200 female patients with breast cancer were involved. All mammography studies were interpreted by a radiologist who had experience in breast imaging interpretation. A convenience sampling technique (non-probability sampling) was used to select a sample from a whole population. The total sample size was 200 patients, included female aged 30 years old and more.

Data analysis

Descriptive and inferential analyses were performed using the Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS) (version 24, 2016). Data were analyzed descriptively to explore summary data (total number, mean, median, and standard deviation). The relationship between age groups and the result of suspicious mass was assessed using non-parametric ANOVA (Kruskal-Wallis). Data analyzed with a preset significance level of $\alpha < 0.05$.

Results

This study included 200 females who underwent mammography. Table 1 shows the demographic characteristics of 200 participants including gender, age, and marital status. All 5 participants were female, Married (78.0%, n= 234), and less than half (31.50%, n=61) were with the age of (40-49). Furthermore, analysis of mammography data revealed that the majority of the results were suspicion mass (85.5%, n=171). More than half of them (55%, n=110) are on stage 4 of breast cancer. However, the right site (45.5%, n=90) was the most frequent site among all mammography scanning. (Table 2 shows the mammography results descriptions). Furthermore, by one-way non-parametric ANOVA (Kruskal-Wallis) test, suspicion mass among females was associated with age (p=.000). However, suspicion mass was significant with female patients 40-49 and 50-59 years old. On the other hand, age was not associated (p= 0.102) with the disease stages among the same patients.

Table 1: characteristics of female Patients who underwent mammography screening units(n=200)

Variables	N	(%)
Age (years)		
30-39	21	10.5
40-49	61	30.5
50-59	54	27
60-69	34	17
70-79	24	12
80 and more	6	3
Marital status		
Single	36	18
Married	158	79
Divorce	5	20.5
Widow	1	0.5

Table 2: Description of mammogram data in terms of results, stage, and site (N=200)

Variables	N	(%)
Results		
Suspicion mass	171	85.5%
Calcifications	20	10%
LN enlargements	9	4.5%
The stage for suspicion mass		
Stage 3	61	45%
Stage 4	110	55%
Site		
Right	90	45.5%
Left	63	31%
Both	47	23.5%

Discussion

In this study, we addressed the mammogram s' findings among women who develop breast cancer in Jordan. Our study showed that a mammogram can detect the suspicion mass. However, this result supports the result of the study conducted by Coleman, (2017) which showed that screening with mammography is the best and most effective method to detect breast cancer early. Furthermore, our study found that suspicion mass among females was associated with age, mainly with female patients 40-49 and 50-59 years old compared to a study conducted by Weigel et al., 2016 to assess the effectiveness of screening and included 19563 patients. This study found that the incidence of advanced stages was more among women with age 50-59 years.

Conclusion

Mammography detection of suspension mass of breast cancer is high. Most of the suspicious masses are discovered at stage four. Therefore, management is essential to develop strategies that will enhance the early identification of cancer by mammography, mainly for high-risk women.

Limitation

The sample was obtained from Jordanian Royal Medical Services hospitals.

Recommendations

Sample should be obtained from different sectors as this sample was obtained only from medical royal services.

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